

Evaluation of Adaptive Physical Education, Sports and Health Learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the implementation of adaptive physical education learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan using the CIPP evaluation model (Context, Input, Process, Product). The research participants consisted of the school principal, the deputy principal for curriculum, and physical education teachers at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan. Data collection was conducted using instruments in the form of questionnaires, interviews, observations, and document studies. Data analysis was performed using a descriptive quantitative and qualitative approach. The evaluation results in the context aspect indicate that the learning planning has been well implemented, supported by school policies and a relevant curriculum that meets the needs of students with special needs. Its implementation is quite good, although it is hindered by the adaptation of teaching materials and evaluation. Input evaluation shows that teachers have a good profile but still struggle to adjust methods to the characteristics of students, compounded by limited training, facilities, and teaching resources. Process evaluation reveals that adaptive physical education learning is not optimal, with low participation, inflexible methods, and ineffective feedback, along with minimal innovation and technology as obstacles. Product evaluation indicates that learning outcomes do not meet the established competencies, evaluations are subjective and lack systematic approaches, and obstacles such as low self-confidence and minimal environmental support for physical activities are found.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation, Learning, Adaptive physical education and health

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical Education, Sports, and Health (PJOK) serves as a means to support physical growth, mental development, motor skills, knowledge, and the instillation of values such as attitudes, emotions, sportsmanship, spirituality, and social skills (Apriyano et al., 2022); (Koh et al., 2024). In addition, PJOK also fosters healthy living habits to create a balance between the physical and psychological development of students. The implementation of PJOK learning in schools is aimed at supporting the growth and development process of students. However, in practice, there are still many obstacles faced, such as limited facilities, resources, and the quality of educators, which have not fully met the ideal education standards (Xu et al., 2021); (Anis et al., 2018).

The learning process of Physical Education, Sports, and Health (PJOK) focuses on organizing the learning experiences of students so that they can acquire knowledge and skills effectively. One important aspect of this process is the use of appropriate learning strategies or methods, as well as the selection of media and learning resources that support the achievement of learning objectives. Currently, there are various strategies, models, methods, and learning media that continue to develop and can be utilized to enhance student engagement in learning and to shape competencies that are relevant to the demands of the 21st century (Selvaraj et al., 2021:316).

PJOK is a mandatory subject at all levels of education, including in Special Schools (SLB) that accommodate students with special needs. In SLB, PJOK learning plays an important role in supporting the improvement of health, physical fitness, psychomotor skills, as well as the social and emotional development of students. Therefore, periodic assessment of the PJOK learning process in SLB is very important to determine the effectiveness of the program's implementation.

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Developing a learning plan that aligns with the educational goals of physical education for children with special needs is the responsibility of teachers who have expertise in their field. However, there are various factors that hinder the achievement of these goals. Although the curriculum has been adjusted to the actual conditions in schools, its implementation still faces obstacles. One of the main reasons is the limited competence of teachers in the field of physical education, which affects the lack of attractiveness of the learning process or the mismatch between the implementation of learning and the teaching materials that have been prepared (Amir & Saifuddin, 2017); (Setiawan et al., 2024); (Francesco et al., 2019).

Strategies in managing learning play a crucial role in the overall teaching and learning process. Without proper classroom management, the learning process will not yield optimal achievements, even if planning, organizing, and delivering the material have been well designed. This also applies to physical education learning, which will not run smoothly if classroom management aspects are neglected (Guyadeen & Season, 2016:107). Physical Education and Health (PJOK) is a form of learning that uses fitness movement as a tool to develop and shape individuals holistically, encompassing physical, psychological, and emotional development. In PJOK, an individual is seen as a whole and real entity, not merely viewed from differences in physical or mental abilities (Neville & Makopoulou, 2020:213).

Learning evaluation is closely related to the step-by-step learning activities from teachers to students. Evaluation serves as a bridge to encourage the optimization of the learning process and to measure the success of the learning process in accordance with the National Education Standards (SNP) 2013. The evaluation process includes the collection and analysis of data to improve the effectiveness of education implementation at the national, regional, and school levels. There are various models and forms of evaluation, which, although different, often share similarities in their approaches. One of the quite popular evaluation models is the CIPP model (Context, Input, Process, Product), developed by Stufflebeam, which emphasizes decisionmaking based on the data obtained (Brigili et al., 2021:327).

II. RESEARCH AND METHOD

A. Research Design and Sample

The type of approach used is evaluation research by applying a mixed method wherecombining quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The purpose of this study is to measure the effectiveness of the physical education learning program at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan. this study employs an evaluation design using the CIPP Model (Context, Input, Process, and Product), as this model is considered capable of producing more accurate and objective evaluations (Ngatman et al., 2024); (Suhartanta et al., 2024); (Simorangkir et al., 2022); (Dizon, 2023). This evaluation was conducted at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan, one of the schools located in the Province of North Kalimantan. The research respondents include the school principal, the vice principal for curriculum, and the physical education teachers at the school.

B. Data Collection Techniques and Research Instrument

Data were obtained through questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documentation, all of which were adjusted to the implementation of the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, and Product) evaluation model. The CIPP model emphasizes evaluation that is comprehensive, systematic, and decision-oriented. Therefore, the use of various research instruments in the form of questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documentation have specific objectives that complement each other in each evaluation stage (Context, Input, Process, Product).

C. Data Analysis Techniques

Data was analyzed using a quantitative and qualitative descriptive approach. Quantitative analysis was used to describe the research object based on data obtained directly from the sample or population without generalizing or drawing general conclusions (Sugiyono, 2019:153). Quantitative data analysis was obtained from questionnaires and observations on the CIPP component aspects studied using SPSS application. Qualitative data analysis was conducted through the formulation of an interactive model to process and understand the meaning of the collected data (Maksum, 2018:136).

III. RESULT

SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan is one of the schools located in the province of North Kalimantan, specifically in Binusan, Nunukan. As of February 7, 2025, the total number of male students is 61 and female students is 31, with a total of 11 teachers.

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a. The results of the adaptive PJOK learning evaluation questionnaire generally show the following data:

The results of the learning evaluation questionnaire are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Achievement Standards in the evaluation of the adaptive PJOK learning process at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

No	Evaluation Aspect	Score	Criteria
1	<i>Context</i>	3,13	Good
2	<i>Input</i>	3,20	Good
3	<i>Process</i>	2,30	Poor
4	<i>Product</i>	2,08	Poor
CIPP Evaluation		2,67	Good

If presented in a line diagram format, the evaluation results of the adaptive physical education learning implementation at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan based on the CIPP model (Context, Input, Process, and Product) can be illustrated as follows:

Figure 1. Diagram of achievement of learning evaluation success criteria

Referring to the figure above, the overall evaluation results of the adaptive PJOK learning program at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan show an average score of 2.67, which is categorized as Good. The details of the evaluation results for each component are as follows:

- Context evaluation received a score of 3.13 and is categorized as good
- Input evaluation achieved a score of 3.20, which is also included in the good category
- Process evaluation obtained a score of 2.30 and is categorized as poor
- Product evaluation received a score of 2.80, which is also categorized as poor

b. The results of the adaptive PJOK learning evaluation interviews are summarized in the following data:

The interview process involved three informants, namely the principal, the curriculum vice principal, and the PJOK teacher at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan. The conclusions from the interviews indicate that the learning outcomes demonstrate that the level of student development in physical education varies and has not fully reached the competencies set in the curriculum. These competencies include the ability to actively participate in demonstrating various variations and combinations of basic movement skills through modified traditional games or sports, as well as the ability to evaluate healthy and active lifestyle attitudes and habits. However, not all students managed to meet these standards, particularly in the psychomotor aspect. The lack of variation in teaching methods contributed to some students not receiving approaches that suited their needs.

c. The results of the adaptive PJOK learning evaluation observations are presented in the data below:

Table 2. Success standards from observations in the assessment of adaptive PJOK learning

No	Evaluation Aspect	Score	Criteria
1	<i>Context</i>	55%	Sufficient
2	<i>Input</i>	48%	Poor

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3	<i>Process</i>	37.5%	Very Poor
4	<i>Product</i>	48%	Poor

Based on the observation results, the assessment of the implementation of adaptive physical education, sports, and health (PJOK) learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan shows that each dimension has varying levels of achievement. Explanations for each stage are presented as follows.

a) Context

The score in the Context dimension reached 55% and is included in the sufficient category. In this aspect, adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri. school policies as well as alignment with student needs. This is demonstrated through the use of a curriculum that refers to applicable standards and is sufficiently relevant to the conditions of the learners. In addition, the school supports the implementation of Adaptive PJOK through appropriate policies and adequate time allocation, and teachers have understood the important role of physical education for students with special needs.

b) Input

The score in the Input dimension reached 48% and is categorized as insufficient. Support for the implementation of adaptive PJOK learning is still limited, especially in terms of facilities, training for teachers, and the availability of systematic learning resources. Teachers have not received adequate training to apply teaching methods that are tailored to the characteristics of the students. In addition, the available materials and teaching resources are inadequate, resulting in the learning process often being carried out improvisationally without a clear reference.

c) Process

The score in the Process dimension is 37.5% and falls into the very poor category. In this aspect, the Adaptive PJOK learning still faces various obstacles, especially in implementation in the classroom and student participation. Although teachers have made efforts to adjust teaching methods to meet students' needs, the execution has not been optimal. The level of student involvement in physical activities is still very low, particularly for those with physical and social barriers. The lack of engaging and innovative teaching strategies also affects students' low motivation to actively participate in learning.

d) Product

The score in the Product dimension reached 48% and is categorized as poor. The Adaptive PJOK learning has not shown a significant impact on the development of students. Although some students have experienced slight improvements in basic motor skills and have begun to show interest in simple physical activities, the majority still cannot meet the competencies set out in the curriculum. The confidence level of the students is also still low, especially when participating in more complex physical activities.

IV. DISCUSSION

a. The results of the evaluation of the adaptive PJOK learning context at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

Based on the research results, the evaluation of the Context stage in adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan shows that the aspects of teaching materials, formulation and learning objectives, design of learning activities, as well as assessment and evaluation have been developed well. The results of the questionnaires and interviews indicate a good category, while the observation results are in the sufficient category. This reflects that conceptually, the learning planning is quite adequate. However, in its implementation in the field, several obstacles are still found.

The context dimension in learning evaluation assesses the extent to which learning objectives are designed systematically and in accordance with the needs of learners (Von Davier et al., 2019). Research findings indicate that the adaptive PJOK learning objectives in special schools have been formulated quite clearly and are in line with the curriculum, particularly in providing flexibility for students with special needs. However, findings from observations that fall into the adequate category indicate that the implementation of teaching materials and learning strategies in the classroom still needs to be improved to be more relevant to real situations in the field (Mohebbi et al., 2011:3272).

Overall, the findings indicate that the evaluation of the Context dimension in Adaptive PJOK learning reflects a fairly good planning. However, its implementation in the classroom still requires improvement. To enhance the effectiveness of learning, it is necessary to make adjustments to more flexible strategies, utilize a more diverse range of teaching materials, and strengthen the evaluation system to be more responsive to the needs of individual students with special needs (Lübke et al., 2021). With these efforts, it is hoped that Adaptive PJOK learning can provide more optimal results for students at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan.

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b. The results of the evaluation of adaptive PJOK learning inputs at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

Based on the research findings, the evaluation of the Input dimension in adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan, which includes teacher profiles and student characteristics, shows varied results. The questionnaire indicates a good category, suggesting that in general, teachers feel they have met the qualifications and understand the needs of students with special needs. However, findings from interviews that were less satisfactory and observation results that fall into the poor category indicate a gap between the teachers' theoretical understanding and its application in classroom learning practices.

This is in line with the findings (Priyono, 2016:5); (Anderson et al., 2021); (Araqi et al., 2022) which state that the main challenge in Adaptive Physical Education (PJOK) lies in adjusting the learning process to the motor and sensory abilities of each student individually. Therefore, although based on the results of the teacher profile questionnaire in Adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan is rated quite well, the results of interviews and observations reveal that there are still gaps in the implementation of learning in the classroom.

c. The results of the evaluation of adaptive PJOK learning Process at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

Based on the research results, the evaluation of the Process dimension in Adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan, which includes the implementation of physical education activities and student participation, shows results that are not yet optimal or unsatisfactory.

An effective physical education learning model must use methods that are tailored to the students' abilities, involve active student engagement, and modify activities so that all students can participate (Chu et al., 2022:5); (Bertills et al., 2019); (Curran & Standage, 2017). However, the research results indicate that the current learning activities have not successfully encouraged optimal active participation from students, which may be due to the limited variety of teaching methods and minimal adjustments in physical activities (Moya & Cara, 2021:14).

The observation results categorized as very poor indicate that the lesson plans that have been made have not been implemented well, both in terms of teaching strategies and student involvement. Constraints such as minimal use of learning media, limited activity modifications, and lack of guidance have caused many students to struggle to participate optimally. Research by (Naz & Murad, 2017:4) also reveals that the main challenge in Adaptive PJOK is the lack of innovation in teaching methods that can be tailored to the diverse needs of students.

The conclusion from the evaluation results in the Process dimension shows that the implementation of Adaptive PJOK learning at SLB is not yet effective, both in terms of teaching methods and student participation. To improve the quality of the learning process, more innovative and interactive methods need to be applied, utilizing technology as an aid, and adopting a more personal approach in guiding students. In addition, schools need to provide additional training for teachers to enhance their skills in adapting learning, so that all students can actively contribute based on their individual abilities.

d. Evaluation results of the product of adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan

Based on the research results, the evaluation of the Product dimension in Adaptive PJOK learning at SLB Negeri 1 Nunukan, which includes assessment of the process and learning outcomes, shows that the achievements are still not optimal.

According to (Stufflebeam, 2017) in the CIPP evaluation model, the Product dimension functions to assess the extent to which learning outcomes align with curriculum goals and their impact on students. Evaluation in this aspect reflects the quality of services provided by teachers and schools in the implementation of the Adaptive PJOK learning program. This finding is consistent with the research results (Lim et al., 2022) which explain that the lack of adaptive assessment instruments in Adaptive PJOK causes difficulties in measuring students' development comprehensively.

The conclusion from the evaluation in the Product dimension shows that the learning outcomes of Adaptive PJOK still require improvement, especially regarding the clarity of assessment instruments, fairness in evaluation, and the effectiveness of the assessment methods applied. To enhance the quality of evaluation, a more comprehensive and flexible assessment system needs to be developed.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The research results on Context Evaluation reveal that the learning planning has been carried out well, supported by school policies and curriculum suitability for students with special needs. Field observations indicate that the implementation of the planning is also going quite well, although there are constraints in adjusting teaching materials and evaluation methods. Input Evaluation reveals that

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the teacher profile is classified as good, but interviews and observations uncover challenges in adjusting teaching methods to the characteristics of students. The main constraints include a lack of teacher training, limited facilities, and minimal learning resources that are relevant to the needs of special students.

Evaluation of the Process, the implementation of Adaptive PJOK learning has not been optimal, indicated by the low participation of students, inflexible teaching methods, and ineffective feedback from teachers. The lack of innovation in learning strategies and minimal utilization of technology are hindering factors. Meanwhile, Product Evaluation shows that the learning outcomes of Adaptive PJOK have not fully met the competencies set by the school, namely the ability of students to actively participate in various variations and combinations of basic movement skills through modified traditional games or sports, as well as the ability to evaluate attitudes and habits of healthy and active living. The evaluations conducted are subjective and less systematic, making it difficult to accurately measure student development. In addition, the lack of self-confidence among students and minimal environmental support in encouraging physical activity are the main obstacles to achieving learning outcomes.

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